



Missing height due to broken tips was estimated by extrapolating the regular, conical shape of the shells and measuring the distance from the virtual tip to the broken edge of the shell in direction parallel to the columella. From this height, the amount of time missing from the record was estimated from the relationship between shell height and age from the isotope measurements closest to the broken edge using the shell model inherited from Judd et al., 2018 (see main text and S13)